
TOWARDS EFFICIENT BIM USE OF UNDERGROUND GEOTECHNICAL DATA

Mohamad El Sibaii

Supervisor

Miguel Azenha⁽¹⁾

(1) University of Minho, ISISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimarães, Portugal

Abstract

The Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry has, recently, abandoned the use of traditional methods and chose to focus on collaborative processes based on Building Information Modeling (BIM) that in turn brought many benefits to construction. Within these benefits, greater sustainability can be highlighted, with fewer risks, better management, and better performance in constructions. The move to BIM started in the context of buildings, subsequently extending to the infrastructure sector as well. In this study, it was intended to make use of BIM programming technologies and data sharing methodologies, to improve the way geotechnical data is used and preserved. Particular attention will be paid to the appropriate definition of specific 'Product Data Templates' (PDT). Proposals to be submitted will also comprise specific precautions concerning Industry Foundation Class (IFC) interoperability. Specifically, this study aims to propose a methodology for using information extracted from surveys and geotechnical reports in a BIM context. In this context, a PDT is proposed as a standard for storing survey data. The methodology includes a program specifically developed on a BIM platform that will use data consistent with the PDT to generate a visual representation of boreholes and underground layers, automatically attaching data to the modeled boreholes.

Dissertation:

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Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/cp00wpR8R4k>

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